

Determining Social Studies Teachers' Competencies in Organizing Out-of-School Learning Environments and the Problems They Encounter During the Implementation Process

Sosyal Bilgiler Öğretmenlerinin Okul Dışı Öğrenme Ortamlarını Düzenleme Yeterlilikleri ile Uygulama Sürecinde Karşılaştıkları Sorunların Belirlenmesi

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to determine the competencies of social studies teachers in organizing out-of-school learning environments and to identify the challenges they encounter during the implementation process of such activities. The research was conducted using a mixed-methods design. The study was carried out with social studies teachers working in public middle schools in the Ergani, district of Diyarbakır, during the 2025–2026 academic year. Quantitative data were collected from 67 teachers, while qualitative data were gathered from 23 teachers. Data collection tools included the “Out-of-School Learning Regulation Scale” developed by Bolat and Köroğlu (2020) and a semi-structured interview form prepared by the researchers. Quantitative data were analyzed using Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis-H tests, while qualitative data were examined through content analysis. The findings revealed that teachers' competencies in organizing out-of-school learning environments did not differ significantly in terms of age, gender, and professional career, but showed significant differences regarding years of professional experience. Furthermore, teachers faced several challenges in organizing out-of-school learning activities, such as “time,” “cost,” “workload,” “safety,” “administrative and bureaucratic procedures,” “curriculum constraints,” and “parental approval and participation.” Among these, time-related issues were identified as the most pressing problem. Therefore, it is recommended that both researchers and educational authorities address the problem of time management, considering the current curriculum in order to develop effective solutions.

Keywords: Social Studies Education, Teacher, Out-of-School Learning, Competence, Challenges

ÖZET

Bu çalışmanın amacı, sosyal bilgiler öğretmenlerinin okul dışı öğrenme ortamlarını düzenleme yeterliliklerini ve okul dışı öğrenme aktivitelerini uygulama sürecinde karşılaştıkları problemleri saptamaktır. Çalışma konusu karma yöntemle dayalı olarak araştırılmıştır. Çalışma, 2025-2026 eğitim-öğretim yılında Diyarbakır/Ergani ilçesinde devlet ortaokullarında görev yapan sosyal bilgiler öğretmenleriyle gerçekleştirilmiştir. Çalışmanın nicel verileri 67; nitel verileri ise 23 sosyal bilgiler öğretmeni üzerinden toplanmıştır. Çalışmada veri toplama aracı olarak Bolat & Köroğlu (2020) tarafından geliştirilen “Okul Dışı Öğrenmeyi Düzenleme Ölçeği” ve araştırmacılar tarafından geliştirilen yarı yapılandırılmış görüşme formu kullanılmıştır. Nicel veriler Mann-Whitney U ve Kruskal-Wallis-H testi; nitel veriler ise içerik analizi tekniği aracılığıyla çözümlenmiştir. Araştırma sonucunda, sosyal bilgiler öğretmenlerinin okul dışı öğrenme ortamlarını düzenleme yeterliliklerinin yaş, cinsiyet ve mesleki kariyer değişkenleri açısından anlamlı farklılık göstermediği; mesleki kıdem değişkeni kapsamında ise anlamlı farklılık gösterdiği saptanmıştır. Ayrıca, sosyal bilgiler öğretmenlerinin okul dışı öğrenme ortamlarını düzenleme sürecinde “zaman”, “maliyet”, “iş yükü”, “güvenlik”, “idari ve bürokratik işlemler”, “eğitim müfredatı” ve “veli onayı ve katılımı” sorunlarıyla karşı karşıya kalmış oldukları saptanmıştır. Uygulamalar sürecinde zaman probleminin en büyük sorun olarak saptandığı bundan dolayı zaman probleminin çözümüne yönelik gerek araştırmacıların gerekse yetkili mercilerin mevcut eğitim müfredatını da göz önünde bulundurarak gerekli çalışmaları yapmaları önerilmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sosyal Bilgiler Eğitimi, Öğretmen, Okul Dışı Öğrenme, Yeterlilik, Sorunlar

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INTRODUCTION

The multidimensional transformations occurring in society and the quest for educating qualified individuals have led to significant changes in the field of education, as in many other domains. One of the main reasons for this transformation is the recognition that limiting teaching and learning activities to the boundaries of the school alone is not sufficient for achieving effective learning outcomes (Durnacı & Ültay, 2020; Chawla & Flanders Cushing, 2007). The increasing significance of out-of-school educational strategies, the growing need for learning environments that establish connections with social realities, and the expanding emphasis on student-centered approaches that prioritize experiential learning have all contributed to the rising importance of out-of-school education practices (Glowinski & Bayrhuber, 2011). Out-of-school education refers to the process of achieving intended knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors within the framework of constructivist learning practices. This approach encompasses diverse learning experiences that take place in museums, historical sites, natural environments, and various institutions and organizations (Henriksson, 2018; Dere & Çifçi, 2022; Vaughan, 2020).

Equipping individuals with the competencies required by the 21st century is of critical importance from both individual and societal perspectives. The educational models adopted play a vital role in shaping such individuals. Experience-based active learning is among the contemporary approaches that serve this purpose (Bozdoğan, 2016). Although active learning is a multifaceted approach, out-of-school learning activities represent a crucial component of it. These activities make significant contributions to students' cognitive, affective, and behavioral development. In other words, they enable students to learn by doing and experiencing, to concretize learning activities, and to engage in educational practices in an enjoyable manner, thereby facilitating the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and values targeted by the curriculum (İnce & Akcanca, 2021; Hooper-Greenhill, 2007; Saraç, 2017).

Social studies education, encompassing a wide range of content such as politics, history, culture, and citizenship, represents a field of study that is inherently intertwined with real-life phenomena (Hughes, Makara, & Stacey, 2020). The primary aim of this multifaceted discipline is to foster active citizens who internalize democratic values, while also enabling learners to develop a deeper understanding of the past, a more comprehensive interpretation of the present, and a clearer foresight into the future (NCSS, 1994). The ongoing efforts to realize these educational objectives, as well as the imperative to nurture individuals equipped with the competencies required in the 21st century, underscore that social studies cannot be effectively taught through theoretical instruction and classroom-based practices alone (Clarke, Sears, & Smyth, 1990). Consequently, removing barriers that restrict students' holistic learning and encourage passivity, while creating opportunities for engagement with authentic, real-life contexts aligned with the curriculum, constitutes a fundamental aspect of teaching social studies effectively (Bunting, 2006). In this regard, the effective instruction of social studies can be achieved through the dynamic and integrated implementation of both classroom-based and out-of-school learning activities.

The social studies curriculum, in terms of its scope and interdisciplinary nature, inherently incorporates out-of-school education practices. Such activities enable students to connect theoretical knowledge acquired in the classroom with real-life contexts, utilize multiple senses, interact directly with authentic resources, explore through discovery, and achieve permanent learning outcomes. In this respect, out-of-school educational practices play a crucial role in fostering long-lasting learning in social studies (Eshach, 2007; Seyhan, 2020). Despite the well-documented advantages of out-of-school learning and the emphasis on their necessity, current educational practices reveal that such activities are not sufficiently implemented. Instead, learning tends to remain at the cognitive level and is predominantly carried out through teachers, textbooks, and digital technologies (Üztemur, Dinç & Acun, 2018; Seyhan, 2020).

A review of the literature shows that numerous national and international studies have examined the significance of out-of-school learning environments and their effects on educational processes. However, there appears to be no research specifically focusing on social studies teachers' competencies in organizing out-of-school learning activities and the problems they encounter during implementation. Therefore, this study is expected to fill a gap in the literature by revealing teachers' professional

competencies in this area, identifying the challenges they face in organizing such activities, and providing insights for future research and practice.

The purpose of this study is to investigate social studies teachers' competencies in organizing out-of-school learning environments and to identify the problems they encounter during the implementation of these activities. In line with this aim, the following research questions will be addressed.

1. What are the arithmetic mean scores of the participants within the scope of the scale?
2. Do the participants' scores on the scale differ relation to the gender variable?
3. Do the participants' scores on the scale differ relation to age variable?
4. Do the participants' scores on the scale differ relation to professional seniority variable?
5. Do the participants' scores on the scale differ relation to professional career status variable?
6. What are the problems encountered by participants in the process of organizing out-of-school learning environments?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study was conducted using a mixed-methods design, combining quantitative (survey model) and qualitative (interview technique) approaches. A mixed-methods design enables the investigation of the research topic in a multidimensional and in-depth manner, allows for examining the consistency and divergence between findings, compensates for the limitations of a single method, and facilitates the generation of new and more complex insights (Bamberger, Rugh, & Mabry, 2006).

Study Group

The population of this research consisted of 96 social studies teachers employed in public middle schools affiliated with the Ergani District Directorate of National Education in Diyarbakır during the 2025–2026 academic year. The sample included 67 social studies teachers.

Table 1: Participants' Characteristics

Teacher Characteristics	Study Group	
	f	%
Gender		
Female	19	28.35
Male	48	71.64
Age		
20-30	5	7.46
31-40	33	49.25
41-50	25	37.31
51-60	4	5.97
61 and above	-	-
Years of Professional Experience		
1-5	3	4.47
6-10	11	16.41
11-15	25	37.31
16-20	20	29.85
21 years and above	8	11.94
Professional Career Status		
Teacher	14	20.89
Specialist Teacher	44	65.67
Head Teacher	9	13.43
Total	67	100

Data Collection Instruments

For the quantitative dimension, data were collected using the Out-of-School Learning Regulation Scale developed by Bolat & Koroğlu (2020). The scale consists of four sub-dimensions “knowledge,” “planning,” “implementation,” and “evaluation.” The arithmetic mean scores of the scale were interpreted as follows:

- Strongly Agree: 4.21-5.00,
- Agree: 3.41-4.20,
- Undecided: 2.61-3.40,
- Disagree: 1.81-2.60,
- Strongly Disagree: 1.00-1.80.

For the qualitative dimension, a semi-structured interview form was developed by the researchers. During the development process, expert opinions were sought to ensure the validity of the form.

Data Collection Process

The data were collected during the 2025–2026 academic year from social studies teachers working in public middle schools affiliated with the Ergani District Directorate of National Education. Accessibility and voluntary participation were prioritized during data collection. All administered scales were deemed valid, resulting in a total of 67 participants for the quantitative dimension. In addition, qualitative data were obtained from 23 teachers through semi-structured interviews.

Data Analysis

The quantitative data were analyzed using non-parametric statistical tests, specifically the Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis-H tests, as the data did not meet the assumptions required for parametric tests. The qualitative data were analyzed through content analysis.

FINDINGS

This section presents the statistical analyses and interpretations of the data obtained in line with the objectives of the study.

1. This section presents the statistical analyses and interpretations of the data obtained in line with the objectives of the study. Within the scope of the research first question “What are the arithmetic mean scores of the participants within the scope of the scale?”, the findings obtained from the analyses are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Participants’ Arithmetic Mean Scores Related to the Scale

Out-of-School Learning Regulation Scale	N	\bar{x}	Sd
Overall Scale	67	4.05	.37
Knowledge Sub-dimension	67	4.08	.42
Planning Sub-dimension	67	3.93	.49
Implementation Sub-dimension	67	4.17	.41
Evaluation Sub-dimension	67	4.02	.45

When the data in Table 2 are examined, it is determined that the participants obtained arithmetic mean scores of $\bar{x}=4.05$ for the overall scale, $\bar{x}=4.08$ for the knowledge sub-dimension, $\bar{x}=3.93$ for the planning sub-dimension, $\bar{x}=4.17$ for the implementation sub-dimension, and $\bar{x}=4.02$ for the evaluation sub-dimension. This finding indicates that the participants’ competencies in organizing out-of-school learning environments are generally at a “good” level ($\bar{x}= 4.05$). On the other hand, it is observed that participants’ perceptions are lowest in the planning sub-dimension and highest in the implementation sub-dimension.

2. Within the scope of the second research question “Do the participants’ scores on the scale differ relation to the gender variable?”, the findings obtained from the analyses are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Mann-Whitney U Test Results Regarding Social Studies Teachers’ Scores in Terms of the Gender Variable

Gender	N	Mean rank	Sum of ranks	U	Z	P
Female	19	29.45	559.50	369.500	-1.204	.228
Male	48	35.80	1718.50			

The data presented in Table 3 indicate that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean rank scores of female and male social studies teachers on the *scale* ($U=369.500$; $z=-1.204$; $p>0.05$).

3. The findings obtained from the analyses conducted to address the third question ‘Do the participants’ scores on the scale differ relation to age variable?’ are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Kruskal-Wallis-H Test Results Regarding Social Studies Teachers’ Scores in Terms of the Age Variable

Groups	N	Mean rank	X2	Df	P
20-30	5	39.80	1.000	3	.801
31-40	33	31.86			
41-50	25	35.36			
51-60	4	35.88			
61 and over age	-	-			
Total	67				

As shown in Table 4, the results of the analysis reveal that the mean rank scores of social studies teachers on the *Out-of-School Learning Organization Scale* do not differ significantly across age groups ($\chi^2=1.000$, $df=3$; $p>0.05$).

4. The findings obtained from the analyses conducted to address the fourth research question ‘Do the participants’ scores on the scale differ relation to professional seniority variable?’ are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Kruskal-Wallis-H Test Results Regarding Social Studies Teachers’ Scores in Terms of the Professional Seniority Variable

Groups	N	Mean rank	X2	Df	P
1-5	3	46.17	12.131	4	.016
6-10	11	36.91			
11-15	25	26.10			
16-20	20	43.83			
21 and over years	8	25.56			
Total	67				

The data in Table 5 indicate that social studies teachers’ competencies in organizing out-of-school learning environments significantly differ according to professional seniority ($\chi^2=12.131$; $df=4$; $p<0.05$). To determine between which groups the differences occurred, the Mann-Whitney U test was conducted. The findings obtained from the analyses are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Mann-Whitney U Test Results Identifying Between-Group Differences Regarding the Professional Seniority Variable

Groups	N	Mean rank	Sum of ranks	U	Z	P
11-15 year	25	17.78	444.50	119.500	-2.984	.003
16-20 year	20	29.53	590.50			

As can be seen in Table 6, the analysis revealed that the significant difference was between the groups with 11–15 years (Mean rank=17.78) and 16–20 years (Mean rank=29.53) of professional seniority, in favor of the latter ($U=119.500$; $z=-2.984$; $p<0.05$).

5. The findings obtained from the analyses conducted to address the fifth research question ‘Do the participants’ scores on the scale differ relation to professional career status variable?’ are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Kruskal-Wallis-H Test Results Regarding Social Studies Teachers’ Scores in Terms of the Professional Career Status Variable

Groups	N	Mean rank	X2	Df	P
Teacher	14	38.36	2.408	2	.300
Specialist Teacher	44	34.34			
Head Teacher	9	25.56			
Total	67				

The data in Table 7 demonstrate that the mean rank scores obtained by social studies teachers from the *Scale* do not differ significantly with respect to the professional career status variable ($\chi^2=2.408$; $df=2$; $p>0.05$).

6. The findings obtained from the analyses conducted to address the sixth research question ‘What problems do social studies teachers encounter in the process of organizing out-of-school learning environments?’ are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Codes Determined Related to Problems Encountered in the Implementation Process

Theme / Category	Code	f	%
The Challenges of Implementation	Time	21	91.30
	Educational curriculum	14	60.86
	Safety	16	69.56
	Cost	19	82.60
	Administrative and bureaucratic processes	15	65.21
	Parental consent	11	47.82
	Workload	18	78.26

Based on the codes and teacher statements presented in Table 8, it was determined that 91.30% of teachers faced time constraints in organizing out-of-school learning activities, 60.86% expressed concerns about covering the curriculum due to its intensity, 69.56% reported safety concerns during implementation, 82.60% emphasized high costs (transportation, materials, equipment, etc.) that discouraged teachers, students, and administrators, 65.21% highlighted complicated and time-consuming administrative and bureaucratic procedures, 47.82% reported lack of parental approval or participation due to safety, economic, or awareness-related reasons, and 78.26% stated that such activities created additional workload.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The findings of the study can be summarized as follows: Participants' competencies were found to be at a "good" level ($\bar{x}=4.05$) for the overall scale. Among the sub-dimensions, the highest score was obtained in implementation ($\bar{x}=4.17$), followed by knowledge ($\bar{x}=4.08$), evaluation ($\bar{x}=4.02$), and planning ($\bar{x}=3.93$). Gül & Saz (2023) similarly concluded that teachers from different subject areas had competencies "above the medium level," which is consistent with the findings of this study.

No significant difference was found in teachers' competencies with respect to gender ($U=369.500$; $z=-1.204$; $p>0.05$). Previous studies across different school levels and subject areas also reported no significant difference in competencies by gender (Uçak & Acar, 2023; Cirit Gül, Tağrikulu & Çobanoğlu, 2023; Usta & Akgül, 2024), supporting the present findings. Similarly, both age ($\chi^2=1.000$, $df=3$; $p>0.05$) and professional career status ($\chi^2=2.408$, $df=2$; $p>0.05$) were found not to have a significant effect.

A significant difference was found with respect to professional seniority ($\chi^2=12.131$; $df=4$; $p<0.05$), specifically between the groups with 11–15 and 16–20 years of experience, in favor of the latter ($U=119.500$; $z=-2.984$; $p<0.05$). This is consistent with the findings of Gül & Saz (2023), who reported that professional seniority significantly affected competencies in the planning dimension.

The most frequently reported problems in organizing out-of-school learning activities, from highest to lowest, were: "time," "cost," "workload," "safety," "administrative and bureaucratic processes," "curriculum demands," and "parental consent and participation." Related studies in the literature similarly highlight issues such as administrative obstacles and safety concerns (Karbeyaz, Karlı & Kurt, 2023), legal procedures (Kubat, 2018), financial burdens, classroom management, and parental issues (Yıldız, 2022; Arslan, 2023; Dere & Çifçi, 2022). These findings overlap with the present results, suggesting that such challenges are common and recurring. Based on these findings, it is recommended that future research further investigate the reasons behind the significant differences arising from professional seniority, examine the topic across different school levels and additional variables, and conduct in-depth analyses of the underlying causes of the problems encountered during the implementation of out-of-school learning activities.

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